

Enhancing Shoreline Stability with a Hybrid Artificial Reef Structure

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1 Introduction

A portion of Seven Mile Beach (SMB) in Grand Cayman Island is fronted by a fringing reef of beach rock. A coastal management project aimed at removing the beachrock to improve the recreational use of the beach. In this work, we used a combination of numerical models to investigate the impacts on the shoreline stability of removing partially or completely the beach rock and proposed a hybrid artificial reef structure to stabilize the beach.

2 Methodology

First, we used a wave spectral and hydrodynamic coupled model (MIKE SW & HD), including tides and winds, to propagate offshore wave conditions (GROW-FINE Caribbean-2 (GFC-2) Hindcast from Oceanweather), and produce 15 years' wave time series in front of the beach. The model was calibrated against ADCP data from 2015 at a depth of 15m close to the study area. Then, we made computations of the long-shore sediment drift on SMB with a 1D model (LITDRIFT) to assess yearly and seasonal sediment transport. Finally, we setup a MIKE 21 FM Shoreline model (2D SM) [1], that combines a 2D description of the waves, hydrodynamics, and sediment transport, with a one-line description of the shoreline position, to investigate sediment flux patterns induced by complex current circulation over the beachrock. This model ran on a fine local grid with an offshore boundary at 15-meter depth. To reduce the computational time, the offshore wave and tide elevation time series have been pre-processed by replacing the actual conditions during calmer periods with representative wave/tide conditions. All 'events' with large waves were fully retained. The model was calibrated using observed changes in shoreline position from a beach survey campaign conducted in 2017 [2].

3 Results

The calibrated wave model ran 15 years and propagated wave conditions that were extracted in seven locations in front of the study area. Seasonal winds and swells create opposing nearshore currents in summer and winter as waves break in shallower areas along the beach profiles. This was confirmed by the 1D sediment transport model showing a seasonal regime with southward (northward) sediment drift in winter (summer). Around the study area, integration of the sediment fluxes resulted into gross yearly sediment

transport around 6,000 m³/year with an almost null net transport behind the beachrock confirming the current beach stability. The 2D SM model results confirmed observations by reproducing nicely the seasonal beach oscillations behind the beachrock over several years. In absence of the beach rock, the model predicted that the shoreline would quickly retreat by several meters in the following years after removal. A solution that involved a partial removal of the central part of the beach rock along a stretch of 200 meters, resulted in a shoreline retreat of 10 m to 15 m at the location of the opening within a period of 8 years. An alternative solution was further developed by adding a submerged artificial reef 100 meters from the shoreline and a replenishment of the beach. The results showed a stabilization of the beach after a period of approximately 6 years with an overall gain of 8 meters of beach (figure 1).

Figure 1: 10 year-time averaged Shoreline differential compared to the baseline for the investigated solutions.

4 Conclusions

The results of our study showed that the partial beach rock removal and the implementation of a breakwater can be used to enhance the recreational value of the area and provide good conditions for swimmers, while limiting impacts to the adjacent shorelines. Moreover, the reef ball elements allow for the reimplantation of corals to compensate for the potential ecosystem loss after removal of the beachrock.

References

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